

Table 3: Effect of Lunch and Dinner on Glycemia in healthy and individuals at high risk for developing or with type 2 diabetes

Study	Health Status Age (years) BMI (kg/m ²)	Duration and design of dietary intervention	Sample size	Description of groups	Dietary intervention	Selected clinical outcomes
Effect of Lunch on Glycemia						
• Lunch timing & Glycemia						
Bandin, <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [161]	Healthy 26±4 22.54±2.05	2 weeks Randomized and crossover (Protocol 1: metabolic study)	10 (subjects on protocol 1)	EE group (Early Eating) LE group (Late Eating)	L at 13:00h L at 16:30h Same B (at 8:00h), D (at 20:00h), and L as indicated 1868±234Kcal/day 15% PRO, 50% CHO, 35% FAT	+46% AUC _{Glu} after L in LE vs EE +1 mmol/L Glu 90min after L in LE vs EE +0.6 mmol/L Glu 120min after L in LE vs EE
Garaulet, <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [164]	Overweight/ obese 42±11 31.4±5.4	20 weeks	420	Early Lunch Eaters (EL) Late Lunch Eaters (LL)	Early eaters: Lunch before 15:00h Late eaters: Lunch after 15:00h Weight loss diet of similar composition Total E ~ 1400 Kcal/d 19% PRO 48% CHO 33% FAT	Fasting Glu (mg/dl) 81.28±15.97 (EL) vs 83.65±16.27 (LL) – non-sign Fasting Ins (mU/l) 5.72±4.71 (EL) vs 6.98±11.66 (LL) – non-sign HOMA 1.17±0.14 (EL) vs 1.57±0.13 (LL) – significant
Effect of Dinner on Glycaemia						
• Dinner timing & composition						
Nas, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [140]	Healthy 24.6±3.3 23.7±4.6	3 test days Randomized crossover	17	Control (C) (3 meals) BSD (B skipping)	Isocaloric diets 55% CHO, 30% FAT, 15% PRO BSD-washout-C-DSD	HOMA_IR 1.96±0.82 (C), 2.07±0.91 (BSD), 1.96±1.05 (DSD) Glycemia _{tAUC} (mg/dLx24h)

		nutritional intervention		DSD (D skipping)	or DSD-washout-C-BSD	<p>2360±111 (C), 2425±131 (BSD), 2374±165 (DSD)</p> <p>MAGE 3.90±1.32 (C), 3.65±1.52 (BSD), 3.28±1.75 (DSD)</p> <p>C-peptide (µg/d) 74±38 (C), 86±40 (BSD), 75±42 (DSD)</p> <p>iAUC_{Ins} (µU/mLx 2h) after L 211±74 (BSD), 144±74 (DSD)</p> <p>iAUC_{Glu} (mg/dLx 2h) after L 114±41 (BSD), 62±40 (DSD)</p> <p>HOMApp after L 59±44 (BSD), 27±23 (DSD)</p>
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [157]	T2D 57.8±4.7 28.1±2.9	5 mo, 14 exp. days Randomized open-label crossover-within-subject clinical trial	18	Bdiet (HE Breakfast) Ddiet (HE Dinner)	<p><u>Bdiet:</u> B – 2946 kJ, 31% PRO, 47% CHO, 22% FAT L – 2523 kJ, 27% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT D – 858 kJ, 43% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT</p> <p><u>Ddiet:</u> B – 858 kJ, 43% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT L – 2523 kJ, 27% PRO, 50% CHO, 23% FAT D – 2946 kJ, 31% PRO, 47% CHO, 22% FAT</p> <p>Composition of diets: 6276±105 kJ</p>	<p>-20% total day AUC_{Glu} for Bdiet vs Ddiet</p> <p>+20% total day AUC_{Ins} for Bdiet vs Ddiet</p> <p>+10% total day integrated AUC_{Ins} for Bdiet vs Ddiet</p> <p>-24% peak Glu (mmol/l × min) at 180min after HE B vs HE D</p> <p>+10-19% peak Ins (pmol/l × min) at 30-180min after HE B vs HE D</p> <p>Faster Ins peak (60mins) after B in Bdiet +17% C-peptide (nmol/l × min) after HE B vs HE D</p>

					<p>31% PRO 46% CHO 23% FAT</p> <p>B at ~08:00h L at ~13:30h D at ~19:30h</p>	<p>+35% tGLP-1 (pmol/l × min) at 30min after HE B vs HE D</p> <p>27% iGLP-1 (pmol/l × min) at 30min after HE B vs HE D</p> <p>-13-25% Glu (mmol/l × min) after L in Bdiet vs Ddiet</p> <p>50% higher, and more rapid early prandial Ins in Bdiet after L</p>
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [158]	Overweight/obese 45.8±7.1 32.4±1.8	12 weeks Randomized open-label parallel-arm trial	74	B group D group	<p>B group (700 kcal B, 500 kcal L, 200 kcal D)</p> <p>D group (200 kcal B, 500 kcal L, 700 kcal D)</p> <p>~1400kcal weight loss diets, same macronutrient content and composition</p> <p>B at 6:00-9:00h, L at 12:00-15:00h, D at 18:00-21:00h</p>	<p>Fasting Glu -11.5% (B) vs -4.2% (D)</p> <p>Fasting Ins -51% (B) vs -29% (D)</p> <p>HOMA-IR -57% (B) vs -32.5% (D)</p> <p>HOMA-B -25% (B) vs -17% (D)</p> <p>ISI +163% (B) vs +56% (D)</p> <p>AUC_{Glu} -22% (B) vs -15% (D)</p> <p>AUC_{Ins} -58% (B) vs -30% (D)</p>
Grant, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [159]	Healthy 25±5.4 22.2±1.6	4 days Controlled, parallel study	11	Eating at night group/condition (EN) Not eating at night group/condition (NoEN)	<p>Meals at 19:00h and 01:30h</p> <p>Meals at 09:30h, 14:10h, and 19:00h</p> <p>B was the tolerance test: ↑CHO (↑GI) at 06:30-07:00h</p> <p>Tolerance test and measurement were done on 4 different days: PRE – day before the start of the protocol, SW4 – days of stimulated night work (sleep</p>	<p>EN group:</p> <p>+27% AUC_{Glu} on SW4</p> <p>+69% AUC_{Glu} on RTDS</p> <p>+11% AUC_{Ins} on SW4</p> <p>+35% AUC_{Ins} on RTDS</p> <p>NoEN group:</p> <p>+12% AUC_{Glu} on SW4</p> <p>+2% AUC_{Glu} on RTDS</p> <p>+18% AUC_{Ins} on SW4</p>

					between 10:00-16:00h for all subjects), RTDS – return to daytime schedule	+16% AUC _{Ins} on RTDS Fasting Glu: No significant effects of condition (p = 0.522), day (p = 0.539) or condition × day (p = 0.228) Fasting Ins: No significant effects of condition (p = 0.380), day (p = 0.056) or condition × day (p = 0.958) for fasting glucose and insulin, respectively
Lopez-Minguez, <i>et al.</i> , 2018 [162]	Overweight/obese 42±10 28.42±4.04	2 exp. days, 1 week Randomized, cross-over trial	40	LE group (Delayed dinner or Late Eating) EE group (Advanced dinner or Early Eating) Also divided groups in <i>MTNR1B</i> risk carriers (GG) and non-risk carriers (CC)	LE: D at 23:00h, L at 15:00h, B at 8:00h EE: D at 20:00h, L at 12:00h, B at 8:00h Fixed menu for all meals on exp. days L was 8h before D, with energy content of 650Kcal D was 30-35% of total energy intake, composed of: 15-17% PRO 58-60% CHO 25-27% FAT	<u>In total population:</u> AUC _{Glu} (mmol/L x h) = 284.74±32.67 (LE) vs 269.61±34.8 (EE) <u>Among GG group:</u> AUC _{Glu} (mmol/L x h) = 292.2±33.8 (LE) vs 270.9±30.4 (EE) <u>Among CC group:</u> No significant effect AUC _{Glu} (mmol/L x h) = 277.3±30.5 (LE) vs 268.2±38.2 (EE) Significant interaction between meal timing (EE vs. LE) and genotype (GG vs. CC) for AUC _{Glu}

Abbreviations: T2D: type 2 diabetes; B: Breakfast; L: Lunch; D: Dinner; E: total energy intake; ppd: postprandial; GI: Glycemic Index; Glu: Glucose; Ins: Insulin; AUC: Area Under the Curve; iAUC: incremental area under the curve; CHO: carbohydrates; PRO: proteins; FAT: fats; HOMA: homeostatic model assessment for insulin; ISI: insulin sensitivity index